

Fast and interpretable time series forecasting using Long Short-term Cognitive Networks

Abstract

Long Short-term Cognitive Networks (LSTCNs) are recurrent neural networks for efficient forecasting of univariate and multivariate time series. They consist of a sequential ensemble of Short-term Cognitive Networks (STCNs), each processing a time patch and passing knowledge to the next block. Originally designed to handle long time series, the LSTCNs' performance on shorter, real-world time series remains unexplored. Besides their efficiency, LSTCNs are deemed interpretable to some extent since both neural concepts and weights have a precise meaning in the domain-specific problem. However, determining feature importance goes beyond inspecting the learned weights and requires more advanced post-hoc methods that operate on the network's internal representations. In this paper, we present two main contributions that address these experimental and theoretical research gaps. As the first contribution, we propose the Sparseness-Optimized Feature Importance for Time Series Forecasting (SOFI-TSF) explainer to rank neural concepts in LSTCN models according to their relevance for the forecast. While this explainer can be applied to any forecaster, our proposal includes knowledge-specific methods to initialize the feature ranking to be improved by SOFI-TSF's optimizer. As a second contribution, besides performing a hyperparameter sensitivity analysis, we conducted an extensive comparative analysis contrasting LSTCNs' performance against other forecasters based on recurrent neural networks, transformers, and hierarchical interpolation. In these studies, we used 25 real-world time series datasets at different prediction horizons and the M5 forecasting competition dataset. The simulations show that (i) all SOFI-TSF variants tested in our simulations largely outperform the baselines in terms of fidelity and explanation sparsity, (ii) LSTCNs outperform the other recurrent forecasters in terms of both forecasting error and runtime.

Keywords: time series forecasting, long short-term cognitive networks, feature importance, SOFI explainer.

1 Introduction

Fuzzy Cognitive Maps (FCMs) [Kosko \(1986\)](#) are knowledge-based recurrent neural networks to model complex systems. They are represented as digraphs composed of neural concepts and causal relationships connecting them. Neural concepts are associated with bounded activation values that depend on a nonlinear function, while causal weights are confined to the $[-1,1]$ interval. A distinctive aspect of FCMs is that their

components have a clear meaning for the problem domain, which makes them interpretable from a static viewpoint [Nápoles et al. \(2023\)](#). Concerning their dynamics, after initializing the neurons with pre-defined activation values, recurrent reasoning is performed. In each iteration, the network produces an activation vector containing the activation values of all neural concepts. It is important to mention that FCM models often operate as closed systems, meaning that the network state in the current iteration is computed solely from the state in the previous iteration [Giabbanelli and Nápoles \(2024\)](#). This reasoning process is repeated until the network converges to a fixed point or a maximum number of iterations is reached.

In their origin, FCMs were used for performing scenario analysis where the domain experts were tasked with defining the FCM structure and the initial conditions [Giabbanelli et al. \(2024\)](#). However, their interpretability and recurrent reasoning motivated researchers to design FCM models for other machine learning tasks such as pattern classification [Tyrovolas et al. \(2023\)](#); [Szwed \(2021\)](#); [Nápoles et al. \(2023\)](#), time series classification [Homenda and Jastrzebska \(2020\)](#); [Jastrzebska et al. \(2021\)](#), and time series forecasting [Wang et al. \(2022\)](#); [Orang et al. \(2023\)](#); [Ouyang et al. \(2024\)](#); [Yang et al. \(2024\)](#). In the context of time series forecasting, the inner recurrent reasoning principles of FCM models make them an ideal tool for forecasting in scenarios where some interpretability is desired. In these settings, the network structure is derived from historical data using supervised learning algorithms. For example, in [Al-Hmouz et al. \(2015\)](#), the authors resorted to fuzzy c-means to create granular neural concepts to capture the amplitude and change of amplitude of the time series, while the weight matrix was estimated using a metaheuristic optimizer.

Despite the relative success of FCM-based models devoted to time series forecasting, they fall short for complex problems involving multiple-step-ahead forecasting or lagged effects. There are two primary reasons behind such a subpar performance. Firstly, the approximation capabilities of FCM-based models devoted to machine learning tasks are limited due to the absence of hidden neurons and having bounded weights and neurons' activation values. It should be noted that recurrent systems cannot benefit from quasi-linear activation functions such as the ReLU function since the neurons' activation values might explode. Secondly, FCM-based models often suffer from convergence issues such as unique fixed points where the network produces the same output for any possible input. These settings make long-term predictions almost impossible. Aiming to cope with these issues, the research community has resorted to hybridizations with other deep learning models (see [Sec. 2](#) for more details) such as autoencoders, gated architectures, or attention mechanisms. However, the improved forecasting performance attained through these hybridizations comes at the expense of sacrificing network interpretability to a large extent.

The Long Short-term Cognitive Networks (LSTCNs) [Nápoles et al. \(2022\)](#) are FCM-rooted neural systems for time series forecasting that do not perform any hybridization that could affect their interpretability. LSTCNs can be defined as a sequential ensemble of Short-term Cognitive Networks (STCNs) [Nápoles et al. \(2019\)](#) where each block processes a subset of the time series, also referred to as *time patch*. In this architecture, learning happens within each STCN block such that the learned

knowledge for the current time patch is transferred to the next block to perform reasoning. STCNs were designed to address the learning limitations of traditional FCM models as they neither impose constraints on the weights nor suffer from convergence issues due to their short reasoning. Moreover, STCNs do not compromise the network interpretability since each neural concept represents a time step in a time series. LSTCNs’ forecasting capabilities have proven comparable to state-of-the-art deep learning models for reported case studies, as the ones in [Morales-Hernández et al. \(2022\)](#) and [Grau et al. \(2022\)](#). While the former was devoted to forecasting very long time series, the remaining ones focused on windmill energy production and semiconductor demand, respectively. Despite inviting optimism, these studies are deemed insufficient to assess the predictive power of LSTCNs when operating with real-world time series, which are generally shorter and more challenging to handle by recurrent neural systems due to potential overfitting situations. In terms of interpretability, LSTCNs allow for determining the feature importance by using centrality measures that do not account for the model’s dynamics while failing to produce sparse explanations, as was concluded in [Nápoles et al. \(2023\)](#).

In this paper, we address the lack of empirical validation of LSTCNs’ performance on real-world, shorter time series and their interpretability through two contributions. Firstly, we introduce a time series forecasting explainer termed Sparseness-Optimized Feature Importance for Time Series Forecasting (SOFI-TSF), which ranks problem features according to their conditional contribution to the forecast. Though applicable to any black-box forecaster, SOFI-TSF allows for incorporating heuristics that use the LSTCNs’ internal knowledge structures to generate a ranking that serves as an initial solution. Note that exploiting such knowledge structure is only possible due to the transparency of FCM-rooted models, even if the initial feature ranking leads to subpar explanations. Secondly, we investigate the predictive efficacy and efficiency of the LSTCN model using 25 real-world time series datasets and different prediction horizons and the M5 forecasting competition dataset.

In our study, we begin with a sensitivity analysis to assess the impact of relevant hyperparameters, namely the number of STCN blocks, the aggregation operator employed to transfer knowledge between blocks, and the regularization penalty controlling overfitting. The results show that the number of blocks and the regularization penalty play a major role in performance optimization. We then compare the forecasting accuracy and runtimes of LSTCNs against other recurrent neural forecasters such as the Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU), the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), and the vanilla Recurrent Neural Network (RNN). We also compare our model against the Temporal Fusion Transformer (TFT) and Neural Hierarchical Interpolation for Time Series Forecasting (NHITS) using an excerpt of the M5 forecasting competition dataset relative to the performance of a Light Gradient-Boosting Machine (LightGBM) using the whole dataset. The numerical simulations lead to straightforward conclusions: (i) all SOFI-TSF variants outperform the random and Shapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) baselines in terms of faithfulness and explanation sparsity, and (ii) LSTCNs produce comparable or better forecasting results than the forecasters used in our study while being around 100 times faster to train on average.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Sec. 2 goes over relevant FCM models for time series forecasting, while Sec. 3 introduces the LSTCN model. Sec. 4 presents the SOFI-TSF explainer and four ranking initialization strategies that exploit the network’s knowledge. Sec. 5 presents the experimental methodology devoted to comparing the LSTCNs’ performance against state-of-the-art deep learning models and assessing the quality of explanations. Sec. 6 provides concluding remarks and gives future research directions worth investigating.

2 Related work

In this section, we examine FCM-based models for time series forecasting, analyzing their core contributions and fundamental limitations to identify persistent challenges in the field. We also evaluate hybrid approaches that integrate the FCM formalism with deep learning architectures, assessing whether these combinations successfully balance interpretability with predictive performance or create complex systems that compromise the advantages of FCM’s transparency.

Traditional FCM development relies heavily on expert knowledge for concept definition and weight specification, creating scalability bottlenecks. To address this limitation, [Shan et al. \(2018\)](#) combined fuzzy c-means clustering for automated concept extraction with Particle Swarm Optimization for weight learning. Their approach proved to be quite scalable across diverse benchmark datasets (enrollment, TAIEX, and Wolf’s sunspot series) and eliminates expert dependency in concept definition. However, this automation comes at the cost of interpretability validation, as discovered concepts may not align with domain knowledge, and provides limited guidance for selecting the optimal number of concepts. [Vanhoenshoven et al. \(2018\)](#) tackled the fundamental fixed-point attractor problem in FCM temporal reasoning by integrating ARIMA-inspired elements into the recurrent reasoning rule. More specifically, they used moving averages of concept activation values and correlation-based weight amplification, which successfully enhanced dynamic behavior and forecasting performance. Nevertheless, their method did not provide theoretical convergence guarantees under the modified reasoning rules powering the forecaster.

Later, [Vanhoenshoven et al. \(2020\)](#) introduced a Moore-Penrose inverse-based FCM learning algorithm that achieves deterministic results and significantly reduced execution time compared to iterative optimization methods (such as those based on metaheuristics). While suitable for applications requiring fast training and reproducible outcomes, the algorithm produces detached weight matrices that are difficult to integrate when forecasting new data, creating practical deployment challenges and potentially compromising prediction consistency.

Several studies have enhanced the ability of FCMs to handle uncertainty and specialized time series formats. For example, [Xixi et al. \(2022\)](#) introduced High-order Intuitionistic FCMs (HIFCM) using intuitionistic fuzzy sets and variational mode decomposition for multi-scale feature extraction. This approach successfully captures temporal patterns at different frequencies through neuron-sequence correspondence during reasoning. However, it significantly increases computational complexity, while

lacking clear evidence that intuitionistic fuzzy sets provide better forecasting performance compared to traditional fuzzy representations.

Building on uncertainty quantification advances, [Ouyang et al. \(2025\)](#) developed Interval High-order FCMs (IHFCMs) that replace real-valued weights with interval-valued weights to better capture uncertain causalities in multivariate time series. Their innovative usage of Pedrycz’s *Principle of Justifiable Granularity* [Pedrycz and Homenda \(2013\)](#); [Pedrycz \(2021\)](#) guides the interval weight construction by balancing coverage maximization and specificity enhancement. While this approach successfully addresses uncertainty quantification, the interval optimization process introduces computational overhead and necessitates careful parameter tuning to select the appropriate granularity.

Addressing the correlation-versus-causation limitation in traditional FCMs, [Qin et al. \(2024\)](#) presented a Causal-HFCM framework that integrates the Peter-Clark algorithm with Fisher Z tests for causal relationship discovery, combined with high-order extensions and Huber regression for robustness against outliers in non-stationary series. This approach outperforms traditional FCMs and statistical models across traffic, air quality, and bearing datasets, providing useful causal interpretations rather than spurious correlations. As expected, the causal discovery phase introduces additional computational complexity and relies on statistical independence assumptions that may not hold in all time series contexts.

Concerning multivariate time series forecasting, [Shen et al. \(2021\)](#) transformed FCM learning into a compressed sensing problem using elastic nets for weight computation, while combining HFCMs with Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) for EEG-based human action prediction. Their complex multi-stage pipeline (elastic net + HFCM + CNN) achieves enhanced performance but reduces interpretability, making it difficult to isolate specific component contributions.

Real-world applications often involve non-standard time series formats that require specialized handling. [Orang et al. \(2020\)](#) integrated HFCMs with High-Order Fuzzy Time Series (HOFTS) and Genetic Algorithms (GA) for weight optimization, successfully outperforming traditional methods (HOFTS, Weighted High Order FTS, Probabilistic Weighted FTS) in solar energy forecasting while using fewer neural concepts, leading to improved efficiency and accuracy. However, this three-component hybrid (HFCM + HOFTS + GA) makes it challenging to isolate individual contributions and increases the complexity of parameter tuning. [Hajek et al. \(2020\)](#) employed intuitionistic fuzzy gray sets for interval-valued time series forecasting, thus handling interval uncertainty, while [Luo et al. \(2020\)](#) extended this with intuitionistic FCMs featuring real-time adjustable hesitation degree calculation for high-uncertainty scenarios. Both approaches provide adaptive uncertainty management, but significantly increase computational overhead through the addition of extra fuzzy parameters, lacking systematic validation that these extensions provide substantial improvements over simpler alternatives.

Domain-specific applications have proven the adaptability of FCMs while revealing implementation challenges. [Peng et al. \(2024\)](#) developed Axiomatic Fuzzy Set Fuzzy Cognitive Map (AFS-FCM) with memory for multidimensional air quality prediction, integrating Axiomatic Fuzzy Set theory to extract semantic meteorological concepts

and achieving comparable performance to deep learning methods while providing actionable insights such as quantitative temperature-CO relationships. Despite maintaining interpretability through semantic-level explanations, the approach requires careful tuning of AFS parameters and may struggle with concept extraction in domains lacking clear semantic boundaries. [Wei and Jiang \(2024\)](#) presented temporal FCMs (tFCM) for cognitive state prediction in educational settings, modeling four cognitive states with nonlinear fuzzy membership functions based on synaptic plasticity theory and integrating LSTM networks for temporal dependencies. While successfully detecting learning fluctuation periods and providing interpretable state relationships, the approach introduces significant complexity through the integration of neural network components and specialized cognitive state modeling that may not generalize beyond educational applications.

The integration of FCMs with deep learning architectures has become increasingly prevalent, aiming to combine the interpretability of FCMs with the powerful pattern recognition capabilities of neural networks. Several studies have achieved enhanced forecasting accuracy through various hybridization strategies: [Wu et al. \(2020\)](#) integrated sparse autoencoders with HFCMs for improved feature representation, [Liu et al. \(2023\)](#) employed sequential FCM-GRU-autoencoder blocks for non-stationary series handling, and [Qin et al. \(2023\)](#) developed deep attention FCMs combining LSTM, spatiotemporal FCMs, and temporal FCMs with residual structures preventing gradient issues in long-term backpropagation, and [Wang et al. \(2021\)](#) created multi-layer FCM architectures forming deep neural networks.

Other hybrid developments have introduced more sophisticated architectural combinations. [Jiacheng et al. \(2025\)](#) proposed the Spatial-Temporal Fuzzy Cognitive Map based adaptive Graph Learning model (STFCM-AGL), combining high-order FCMs with granularity adjustment, Adaptive-GraphSAGE for spatial node embeddings, and temporal convolution networks. Although this approach successfully captures both spatial and temporal dependencies, the complex three-component architecture obscures individual contributions and requires extensive hyperparameter optimization across graph learning, temporal modeling, and granularity adjustment components. [Teng et al. \(2024\)](#) developed a LSTM and high-order FCM with an attention mechanism (LSTM-HFCMAM), addressing feature extraction limitations in existing FCM methods by using sliding windows to preserve temporal integrity, combining LSTM encoder-decoder frameworks with self-attention mechanisms for prediction restoration. While achieving improvements over existing methods and mitigating overfitting issues, the integration of three distinct components (LSTM, HFCM and attention mechanism) creates a complex system where the interpretability benefits of FCMs become diluted within the hybrid architecture.

Signal processing hybrid models have also been introduced, with [Qiao et al. \(2022\)](#) combining variational mode decomposition with FCMs and [Yang and Liu \(2018\)](#) integrating HFCMs with redundant wavelet transform to address large-scale non-stationary challenges. While these hybrid approaches achieve performance gains, they severely compromise FCM interpretability by creating "black box" systems where causal reasoning becomes obscured and individual component contributions cannot

be isolated. The increased hyperparameter spaces require extensive tuning, yet lack theoretical frameworks for optimal architecture selection.

After revising the literature, we have noticed that the evolution of FCM-based forecasting methods reveals a fundamental paradox between interpretability and accuracy. For example, current approaches have successfully addressed data uncertainty and enhanced predictive accuracy through algorithmic advances, which provide evidence of the field’s adaptability to diverse forecasting challenges. However, these advances predominantly rely on complex hybridizations with deep learning architectures, which sacrifice FCMs’ fundamental advantage: transparent and explainable causal relationships. This analysis reveals a gap that requires forecasting models to maintain both high accuracy and interpretability without resorting to complexity-inducing hybridizations. This motivates our development of the LSTCN model, which aims to achieve efficient interpretable time series forecasting while preserving the transparent causal reasoning that makes FCMs valuable for practical applications.

3 Long Short-term Cognitive Networks

In this section, we present the theoretical foundations behind the LSTCN model [Nápoles et al. \(2022\)](#). In short, this FCM-rooted forecasting model can roughly be defined as an ensemble of neural blocks, each processing a specific part of the time series and passing information to the subsequent blocks.

Let \mathbf{T} be a multivariate time series dataset, which contains as many columns as features and as many rows as time observations. Moreover, let us assume that \mathbf{T} is split into *time patches* $\mathbf{P}^{(t)} = (\mathbf{X}^{(t)}, \mathbf{Y}^{(t)})$ such that $\mathbf{X}^{(t)}$ is the input and $\mathbf{Y}^{(t)}$ is the output for the current time patch. The shape of $\mathbf{X}^{(t)}$ and $\mathbf{Y}^{(t)}$ is given by $K \times M$ where K is the number of instances in the current time patch, while $M = L \cdot N$ represents the number of neural concepts such that L is the number of steps-ahead to be predicted and N is the number of features describing the time series. There are two relevant aspects to be mentioned. Firstly, this recurrent neural system is symmetric, which means that it will also use the last L observations to compute the following L predictions. Secondly, the model’s complexity (as quantified by the number of learnable parameters) increases linearly with P and quadratically with M . However, there is a trade-off between the network’s complexity and the quality of multiple-step-ahead predictions. In other words, although the model becomes more powerful as M increases, the difficulty of the forecasting problem will inherently rise with the lengthening of the prediction horizon.

While processing the whole time series, each time patch is processed using a Short-term Cognitive Network (STCN) block [Nápoles et al. \(2019\)](#) described by four matrices \mathbf{B}_1 , \mathbf{W}_1 , \mathbf{B}_2 and \mathbf{W}_2 . These matrices correspond with the bias weights (with dimensions $1 \times M$) and the weights between the temporal neural concepts (with dimensions $M \times M$). Notice that each concept is deemed temporal since it processes a specific time step within a time series. For example, if the current time patch processes the first 10 time steps in a multivariate time series composed of three features, then there will be 30 neural concepts. That is why the model’s complexity depends on the number of time steps being processed and the number of features. Moreover, hidden neurons are not permitted, as they would compromise the model’s interpretability.

One relevant feature of LSTCNs is that each processing block passes the learned information to the next block, which is then used to process the following time patch. More explicitly, while \mathbf{B}_1 and \mathbf{W}_1 are initialized using the knowledge learned by the previous STCN model, \mathbf{B}_2 and \mathbf{W}_2 are learned from the data contained in the current time patch. Overall, the forecasting is done as follows:

$$\hat{\mathbf{Y}}^{(t)} = f\left(\mathbf{H}^{(t)}\mathbf{W}_2^{(t)} \oplus \mathbf{B}_2^{(t)}\right) \quad (1)$$

such that

$$\mathbf{H}^{(t)} = f\left(\mathbf{X}^{(t)}\mathbf{W}_1^{(t)} \oplus \mathbf{B}_1^{(t)}\right) \quad (2)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{Y}}^{(t)}$ is a $K \times M$ matrix with the predicted values for the current time patch and $f(\cdot)$ is the activation function, typically the hyperbolic tangent or the sigmoid functions. In this equation, the \oplus operator is devoted to performing a matrix-vector addition between each row of a given matrix with a vector, provided that the matrix and the vector have the same number of columns.

Fig. 1 shows the inner workings of the LSTCN forecasting model when processing a multivariate time series split into three time patches. In this figure, Ψ is an aggregation operator used to obtain the prior knowledge matrix that the current STCN block passes to the next one. It should be stated that after the whole time series has been processed, the last STCN block is used to forecast unseen data.

Fig. 1: LSTCN model processing a multivariate time series split into three time patches. Notice that the matrices learned from the current time patch are used as prior knowledge by the following STCN block.

The aggregation operator Ψ plays an important role in this neural system since it produces the weight and bias matrices to be passed to the following STCN block. It can take one or two arguments and can operate in a linear or nonlinear way. The operators explored in this study are formalized as follows. The *unary linear aggregation* is defined as $\Psi_L(\mathbf{W}_2^{(t)}) = \mathbf{W}_2^{(t)}$ and $\Psi_L(\mathbf{B}_2^{(t)}) = \mathbf{B}_2^{(t)}$. The *unary nonlinear aggregation* is given by $\Psi_N(\mathbf{W}_2^{(t)}) = \tanh(\mathbf{W}_2^{(t)})$ and $\Psi_N(\mathbf{B}_2^{(t)}) = \tanh(\mathbf{B}_2^{(t)})$. The *binary maximum operator* Ψ_{\max} performs an element-wise maximum between two matrices. It takes two matrices of the same dimensions and returns a new matrix where each element is the maximum of the corresponding elements from the input

matrices. This operator is defined as $\Psi_M(\mathbf{W}_1^{(t)}, \mathbf{W}_2^{(t)}) = \max(\mathbf{W}_1^{(t)}, \mathbf{W}_2^{(t)})$ where $[\Psi_M(\mathbf{W}_1^{(t)}, \mathbf{W}_2^{(t)})]_{ij} = \max([\mathbf{W}_1^{(t)}]_{ij}, [\mathbf{W}_2^{(t)}]_{ij})$. Similarly, for $\mathbf{B}_1^{(t)}$ and $\mathbf{B}_2^{(t)}$, we define $\Psi_M(\mathbf{B}_1^{(t)}, \mathbf{B}_2^{(t)}) = \max(\mathbf{B}_1^{(t)}, \mathbf{B}_2^{(t)})$ where $[\Psi_M(\mathbf{B}_1^{(t)}, \mathbf{B}_2^{(t)})]_i = \max([\mathbf{B}_1^{(t)}]_i, [\mathbf{B}_2^{(t)}]_i)$. Finally, the *binary average aggregation* is defined as $\Psi_A(\mathbf{W}_1^{(t)}, \mathbf{W}_2^{(t)}) = 0.5 \cdot \mathbf{W}_1^{(t)} + 0.5 \cdot \mathbf{W}_2^{(t)}$ and $\Psi_A(\mathbf{B}_1^{(t)}, \mathbf{B}_2^{(t)}) = 0.5 \cdot \mathbf{B}_1^{(t)} + 0.5 \cdot \mathbf{B}_2^{(t)}$.

The efficiency of the LSTCN model relies on the fact that learning happens within each STCN block using a shallow learning approach, even when the reasoning is long-term. Eq. (3) displays the deterministic learning rule using ridge regression to compute the learnable matrices within each STCN block,

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{W}_2^{(t)} \\ \mathbf{B}_2^{(t)} \end{bmatrix} = \left(\left(\Phi^{(t)} \right)^\top \Phi^{(t)} + \lambda \Omega^{(t)} \right)^{-1} \left(\Phi^{(t)} \right)^\top f^- \left(\mathbf{Y}^{(t)} \right) \quad (3)$$

where $\Phi^{(t)} = (\mathbf{H}^{(t)} | \mathbf{A})$ such that $\mathbf{A}_{K \times 1}$ is a column vector filled with ones, $\Omega^{(t)}$ represents the diagonal matrix of $(\Phi^{(t)})^\top \Phi^{(t)}$ whereas $\lambda \geq 0$ denotes the ridge regularization penalty. To avoid numerical instability when computing the inverse of $f(\cdot)$, we restricted the output range to $[\epsilon, 1 - \epsilon]$ for the sigmoid function and $[-1 + \epsilon, 1 - \epsilon]$ for the hyperbolic tangent, where ϵ was set to 1.0e-6.

The reader can notice that an STCN block trained using the learning rule in Eq. (3) can be understood as a fusion between an Extreme Learning Machine (ELM) Wang et al. (2021) and an FCM model that performs two iterations. There are two primary differences. On the one hand, the first matrix is not random but initialized with prior knowledge. On the other hand, all neural concepts retain their meaning when it comes to the problem domain being represented.

Algorithm 1 details the steps to create the time patches and the test data from the time series data \mathbf{T} , which contains as many columns as features and as many rows as time observations. The algorithm begins determining the splitting point S based on the specified train-test split ratio and the forecasting horizon L . Specifically, $S = \lfloor split \times len(\mathbf{T}) \rfloor + L$, so the predictions for the first segment in \mathbf{T}_{test} will be done from the last segment in \mathbf{T}_{train} . Notice that we have used the slicing and indexing conventions of Python in this pseudocode. The algorithm iterates over \mathbf{T}_{train} to create training instances. For each time step t , it extracts a sequence of L data points as input $\mathbf{X}_{train}^{(t)}$ and the subsequent L points as output $\mathbf{Y}_{train}^{(t)}$, appending these to their respective lists. A similar process is followed for the testing data to generate input-output pairs from \mathbf{T}_{test} for evaluation purposes. After generating the full sets of training instances, the algorithm computes the number of instances per block Q by dividing the total training instances by the number of STCN blocks (denoted as n_blocks). This step ensures that the data is evenly distributed across STCN blocks while discarding the necessary time observations from the beginning of the time series. Subsequently, the algorithm organizes the training data into disjoint blocks of size Q , forming tuples of input-output pairs for each block and collecting them in a list \mathbf{P} . In the final step, it returns these structured time patches \mathbf{P} alongside the test input-output pairs \mathbf{X}_{test} and \mathbf{Y}_{test} for use in model training and evaluation.

Algorithm 2 summarizes the steps to train an LSTCN model where the time series data \mathbf{T} , the prediction horizon L , the regularization parameter λ , the aggregation

Algorithm 1 Splitting time series \mathbf{T} into time patches

Require: Time series data \mathbf{T} , number of steps-ahead L , number of STCN blocks n_blocks , train-test split ratio $split \in [0, 1]$

- 1: Compute the splitting point $S = \lfloor split \times len(\mathbf{T}) \rfloor + L$
 - 2: Define $\mathbf{T}_{train} = \mathbf{T}[0 : S, :]$ and $\mathbf{T}_{test} = \mathbf{T}[S : len(\mathbf{T}), :]$
 - 3: Create empty lists \mathbf{X}_{train} , \mathbf{Y}_{train} , \mathbf{X}_{test} , and \mathbf{Y}_{test}
 - 4: **for** $t = 0$ to $len(\mathbf{T}_{train}) - (2L - 1)$ **do**
 - 5: Compute the instance input $\mathbf{X}_{train}^{(t)} = \mathbf{T}_{train}[t : t + L, :]$
 - 6: Compute the instance output $\mathbf{Y}_{train}^{(t)} = \mathbf{T}_{train}[t + L : t + 2L, :]$
 - 7: Append $\mathbf{X}_{train}^{(t)}$ to \mathbf{X}_{train} and $\mathbf{Y}_{train}^{(t)}$ to \mathbf{Y}_{train}
 - 8: **end for**
 - 9: **for** $t = 0$ to $len(\mathbf{T}_{test}) - (2L - 1)$ **do**
 - 10: Compute the instance input $\mathbf{X}_{test}^{(t)} = \mathbf{T}_{test}[t : t + L, :]$
 - 11: Compute the instance output $\mathbf{Y}_{test}^{(t)} = \mathbf{T}_{test}[t + L : t + 2L, :]$
 - 12: Append $\mathbf{X}_{test}^{(t)}$ to \mathbf{X}_{test} and $\mathbf{Y}_{test}^{(t)}$ to \mathbf{Y}_{test}
 - 13: **end for**
 - 14: Calculate the instances per block $Q = \lfloor len(\mathbf{X}_{train}) / n_blocks \rfloor$
 - 15: Compute $\mathbf{X}_{train} = \mathbf{X}_{train}[-(Q * n_blocks) :, :]$
 - 16: Compute $\mathbf{Y}_{train} = \mathbf{Y}_{train}[-(Q * n_blocks) :, :]$
 - 17: Create an empty list \mathbf{P} for the time patches
 - 18: **for** $t = 0$ to n_blocks with step Q **do**
 - 19: Compute the block input $\mathbf{X}^{(t)} = \mathbf{X}_{train}[t : t + Q, :]$
 - 20: Compute the block input $\mathbf{Y}^{(t)} = \mathbf{Y}_{train}[t : t + Q, :]$
 - 21: Append the tuple $\mathbf{P}^{(t)} = (\mathbf{X}^{(t)}, \mathbf{Y}^{(t)})$ to \mathbf{P}
 - 22: **end for**
 - 23: **return** $\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{X}_{test}, \mathbf{Y}_{test}$
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operator Ψ , and the activation function f need to be given as inputs. It starts by splitting the time series data \mathbf{T} into time patches $\mathbf{P}^{(t)} = (\mathbf{X}^{(t)}, \mathbf{Y}^{(t)})$ using Algorithm 1. After initializing the matrices $\mathbf{B}_1^{(t)}$ and $\mathbf{W}_1^{(t)}$ randomly or using prior knowledge if available, the algorithm iterates over each time patch t . Within this loop, it computes a hidden representation $\mathbf{H}^{(t)}$ using the activation function f , which transforms a linear combination of the input data $\mathbf{X}^{(t)}$ multiplied by the weight matrix $\mathbf{W}_1^{(t)}$ and the bias matrix $\mathbf{B}_1^{(t)}$. This hidden representation captures the high-level features necessary for predicting the output of the current block. The algorithm then employs ridge regression to compute the weights $\mathbf{W}_2^{(t)}$ and biases $\mathbf{B}_2^{(t)}$, thus fitting the model to the desired outputs $\mathbf{Y}^{(t)}$. Subsequently, it updates the weights and biases for the next iteration by applying the aggregation operator Ψ to the current weights $\mathbf{W}_1^{(t)}$ and $\mathbf{B}_1^{(t)}$ along

with their corresponding output weights $\mathbf{W}_2^{(t)}$ and biases $\mathbf{B}_2^{(t)}$. This iterative process continues for all time patches, ultimately resulting in the learned parameters $\mathbf{W}_1, \mathbf{B}_1, \mathbf{W}_2,$ and \mathbf{B}_2 that characterize the last STCN block.

Algorithm 2 Building and training an LSTCN model

Require: Time series data \mathbf{T} , number of steps-ahead L , regularization parameter λ , aggregation operator Ψ and activation function f .

- 1: Split \mathbf{T} into time patches $\mathbf{P}^{(t)} = (\mathbf{X}^{(t)}, \mathbf{Y}^{(t)})$
- 2: Initialize matrices $\mathbf{B}_1^{(t)}, \mathbf{W}_1^{(t)}$ randomly
- 3: **for** each time patch t in $\mathbf{P}^{(t)}$ **do**
- 4: **Step 1:** Compute hidden representation $\mathbf{H}^{(t)}$ for current patch:

$$\mathbf{H}^{(t)} = f\left(\mathbf{X}^{(t)}\mathbf{W}_1^{(t)} \oplus \mathbf{B}_1^{(t)}\right)$$

- 5: **Step 2:** Update weights $\mathbf{W}_2^{(t)}$ and $\mathbf{B}_2^{(t)}$ using ridge regression:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{W}_2^{(t)} \\ \mathbf{B}_2^{(t)} \end{bmatrix} = \left(\left(\Phi^{(t)} \right)^\top \Phi^{(t)} + \lambda \Omega^{(t)} \right)^{-1} \left(\Phi^{(t)} \right)^\top f^{-1}(\mathbf{Y}^{(t)})$$

- 6: Compute $\mathbf{W}_1^{(t+1)} = \Psi(\mathbf{W}_1^{(t)}, \mathbf{W}_2^{(t)})$ for the next iteration.
 - 7: Compute $\mathbf{B}_1^{(t+1)} = \Psi(\mathbf{B}_1^{(t)}, \mathbf{B}_2^{(t)})$ for the next iteration.
 - 8: **end for**
 - 9: **return** $\mathbf{W}_1, \mathbf{B}_1, \mathbf{W}_2, \mathbf{B}_2$
-

It is worth discussing the difference between LSTCNs' knowledge transfer mechanism and the LSTM's cell state memory. In the case of LSTCNs, the knowledge transference occurs at the level of weight and bias matrices, where the next block's parameters $\mathbf{W}_1^{(t+1)}$ and $\mathbf{B}_1^{(t+1)}$ result from the aggregation operator Ψ applied to the prior block's parameters. In contrast, the LSTM's cell state evolves within a single recurrent unit at every time step by integrating previous memory and new input through gating mechanisms. This latent state update occurs continuously, which maintains a hidden memory representation shaped by learned gates. Thus, LSTCN knowledge transfer is parameter-centric and modular across time patches, while LSTM cell state memory is activation-centric and recurrent within a continuous sequence. This structural difference impacts interpretability, modularity, and the form in which temporal information persists and flows through the models.

4 Sparseness-Optimized Feature Importance

While LSTCNs might be deemed interpretable to some extent since their neurons denote temporal features that align with the problem domain, intrinsically interpretable models often struggle with providing sparse explanations. In this section, we present a post-hoc explanation method for time series forecasters that use the network’s learned parameters to initialize the algorithm.

4.1 Ranking optimization for forecasting tasks

Let (\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}) denote the validation data, where $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{K \times M}$ is the input matrix and $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{R}^{K \times M}$ is the corresponding forecast target. In such validation data, \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{Y} are described by M temporal features arranged across K instances. Temporal features correspond to individual scalar values representing a given original feature at a specific time step, and are denoted by neural concepts in the network.

The rationale of the SOFI-TSF algorithm for time series forecasting is to find a permutation $\mathbf{\Pi} = (\pi_1 \preceq \pi_2 \preceq \dots \preceq \pi_M)$ over the set of temporal features such that a performance degradation score is maximized. Such a post-hoc method assumes that the forecasting $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is trained and ready to be exploited. As for the degradation score, we employ the difference between two performance-marginalization curves that measure the increase in the forecasting error as the temporal features are marginalized (i.e., replaced by a constant value) Šimić et al. (2022); Schulz et al. (2020). The MoRF (Most Relevant First) curve is obtained by sequentially marginalizing temporal features from most to least relevant according to the ranking. Conversely, the LeRF (Least Relevant First) curve is built by marginalizing features from least to most relevant. A ranking is considered good if the MoRF curve rises rapidly while the LeRF curve remains relatively flat, indicating that perturbing the top-ranked features substantially degrades model performance, whereas perturbing the bottom-ranked features has little impact. Therefore, a large degradation core, quantified by the area defined by these two curves, gives a reliable indicator of sparsity in the explanation. In practice, sparse explanations allow for determining which temporal features are responsible for the forecasting.

Let $\mathcal{E}_i(\Gamma(\mathbf{X}), \mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{\Pi}, c)$ denote the forecasting error after marginalizing up to the i -th in the $\mathbf{\Pi}$ ranking with the marginalization constant c . In that regard, the MoRF curve $\mathcal{M}(\Gamma(\mathbf{X}), \mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{\Pi}, c)$ is given by the sequence $\{\mathcal{E}_i(\Gamma(\mathbf{X}), \mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{\Pi}, c)\}_i$ where features in $\mathbf{\Pi}$ are sorted from most to least importance. The LeRF curve $\mathcal{L}(\Gamma(\mathbf{X}), \mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{\Pi}^\wedge, c)$ is given by the sequence $\{\mathcal{E}_i(\Gamma(\mathbf{X}), \mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{\Pi}^\wedge, c)\}_i$ where $\mathbf{\Pi}^\wedge = (\pi_M \succeq \pi_{M-1} \succeq \dots \succeq \pi_1)$ is the reverse of $\mathbf{\Pi}$. The degradation score associated with ranking $\mathbf{\Pi}$ is given by the area between these performance-degradation curves:

$$\mathcal{D}(\Gamma(\mathbf{X}), \mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{\Pi}, c) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=0}^{M-1} ([\mathcal{M}_i - \mathcal{L}_i] + [\mathcal{M}_{i+1} - \mathcal{L}_{i+1}]). \quad (4)$$

When designing explanation methods for time series forecasters, selecting the marginalization constant is difficult. If the constant is too close to the original values, the effect on performance may be too small to reveal feature importance. If it is too far, the perturbation may create unrealistic data that exaggerates performance

degradation. Learning this constant together with the ranking is innovative since it adapts the perturbation to the data and model simultaneously. This joint learning avoids manual tuning and ensures that the degradation score more accurately reflects the true relevance of temporal features for forecasting.

The optimization is performed using hill-climbing (see Algorithm 3). Initially, it receives the trained forecasting model $\Gamma(\cdot)$, the validation data (\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}) , the maximum number of iterations max_iter , a list \mathbf{C} of marginalization constants and optionally a vector of initial scores \mathbf{S} used to build an initial permutation. If no such vector is provided, the initial ranking is chosen randomly.

At each iteration, the algorithm generates a candidate ranking by swapping two randomly selected positions in the current best ranking while sampling the marginalization constant from the list. It then computes the degradation score for the candidate using the validation set. If the evaluation of the current ranking is higher than the best solution found so far, the new ranking replaces the current best. This process continues until reaching the maximum iterations.

Algorithm 3 SOFI-TSF Explainer for Temporal Data

```

1: Input: Forecasting model  $\Gamma(\cdot)$ , validation data  $(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y})$ , marginalization values  $\mathbf{C}$ ,
   feature scores  $\mathbf{S}$  (optional), maximum iterations  $max\_iter$ ,
2: Output: Optimal ranking of temporal features  $\Pi^*$ 
3: if  $\mathbf{s}$  is provided then
4:   Sort features by descending values of  $\mathbf{S}$  to initialize  $\Pi$ 
5: else
6:   Initialize  $\Pi$  as a random permutation of  $\{1, \dots, M\}$ 
7: end if
8: Randomly select a marginalization value  $c$  from  $\mathbf{C}$ 
9: Compute the degradation score  $d_0 = \mathcal{D}(\Gamma(\mathbf{X}), \mathbf{Y}, \Pi, c)$ 
10: Set  $\Pi^* \leftarrow \Pi$ ,  $c^* \leftarrow c$  and  $d^* \leftarrow d_0$ 
11: for  $iter = 1$  to  $max\_iter$  do
12:   Select two distinct indices  $i, j \in \{1, \dots, M\}$  uniformly at random
13:   Generate candidate ranking  $\Pi'$  by swapping positions  $i$  and  $j$  in  $\Pi^*$ 
14:   Randomly select a marginalization value  $c'$  from  $\mathbf{C}$ 
15:   Compute the degradation score  $d' = \mathcal{D}(\Gamma(\mathbf{X}), \mathbf{Y}, \Pi', c')$ 
16:   if  $d' > d^*$  then
17:     Update Set  $\Pi^* \leftarrow \Pi'$ ,  $c^* \leftarrow c'$  and  $d^* \leftarrow d'$ 
18:   end if
19: end for
20: Return: Optimized ranking  $\Pi^*$ 

```

Although SOFI-TSF is a post-hoc explanation method, its design differs substantially from widely used techniques such as SHAP Lundberg and Lee (2017), local surrogates such as LIME Ribeiro et al. (2016), or model-specific post-hoc methods such as DeepLIFT Li et al. (2021). These approaches approximate local feature contributions, but none of them treat sparsity as an explicit optimization target. In contrast,

SOFI-TSF learns a ranking that optimizes for sparsity by maximizing the degradation gap between relevant and irrelevant segments, which yields explanations that are intentionally compact and thus better aligned with the parsimony principle of interpretability. Moreover, SOFI-TSF can incorporate domain knowledge through different initialization heuristics that guide the ranking process, allowing the explanations to reflect structural priors about the time series. Existing post-hoc attribution methods do not offer such a mechanism for injecting prior knowledge into the explanatory process, which makes SOFI-TSF not only methodologically distinct but also more adaptable in settings where expert guidance is available.

4.2 Initial ranking approximation

While the SOFI-TSF explainer can produce high-quality solutions starting from a random permutation, we can improve the search process by exploiting the knowledge of trained LSTM models. This is only possible because all neural concepts and weights have a well-defined meaning for the problem domain. Next, we propose four methods to score the neural concepts of LSTM models given a certain learned weight matrix $\mathbf{W}_2^{(t)}$ and a hidden network state $\mathbf{H}^{(t)}$. These scores will then be used to rank the concepts (mapping temporal features within a fixed time window) and obtain the initial solution to be improved by SOFI-TSF’s optimization steps.

4.2.1 Weight-based importance scores

The first group of explanation methods focuses on the structural connectivity of an LSTM model, as encoded in the learned weight matrices. The rationale of these methods is that the architecture and strength of connections, both direct and indirect, encode how different concepts influence the forecasting. Since the forecasting is computed using the last LSTM block in the ensemble, the corresponding weight matrix will be used for computing the concepts’ scores.

Degree centrality (DC) quantifies the direct influence of a neural concept by measuring the overall strength of its immediate connections to other neurons. For a given neural concept C_i , the total absolute weight of both outgoing and incoming edges for a given learned weight matrix $\mathbf{W}_2^{(t)}$ is computed as follows:

$$\text{DC}(C_i) = \sum_{j \neq i} |w_{ij}^{(t)}| + |w_{ji}^{(t)}|, w_{ij}^{(t)} \in \mathbf{W}_2^{(t)}. \quad (5)$$

According to this weight-based method, a higher degree score indicates that the neural concept exerts or receives strong direct influence. As such, this translates into a prominent role in the model’s forecasting.

Eigenvector Centrality (EC) measures the importance of neural concepts by considering not only their connections but also the influence of those connections. The key intuition behind this scoring method is that a neural concept gains greater significance when it is connected to other highly influential concepts. Formally, EC is computed by solving the following eigenvalue problem:

$$\mathbf{W}_2^{(t)} \mathbf{v}^{(t)} = \lambda^{(t)} \mathbf{v}^{(t)}, \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{v}^{(t)}$ contains the centrality scores and $\lambda^{(t)}$ is the corresponding eigenvalue. A concept C_i with a high entry in $\mathbf{v}^{(t)}$ is not only strongly connected but also connected to other highly central concepts. This recursive formulation emphasizes structurally important concepts within the last STCN block.

4.2.2 Activation-based importance score

This scoring method derives the importance of each neural concept based on its activation values across time patches instead of using the connected weights. The resulting score provides a quantification of how the concepts' activation values evolve as time patches are processed by the network. This approach prioritizes activation dynamics over static connection weights, which would characterize how concepts gain or lose relevance as the network processes sequential data.

The mean activation (MA) method estimates the concept's score by computing the average absolute value of its hidden activation values:

$$\text{MA}(C_i) = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T |\mathbf{H}_i^{(t)}|. \quad (7)$$

Additionally, we can evaluate the importance based on the activation volatility as $\text{VA}(C_i) = \text{Var}(\mathbf{H}_i^{(1)}, \dots, \mathbf{H}_i^{(T)})$. This method highlights concepts whose involvement fluctuates significantly throughout the time patches. A final variant of this method is to capture peak activations as $\text{PA}(C_i) = \max_t |\mathbf{H}_i^{(t)}|$. This variant is particularly suited for detecting concepts that, although not consistently active, may play a relevant role at specific time patches. It can be especially relevant in models that respond sharply to certain events or anomalies in the time series.

4.2.3 Hybrid importance score

The last method integrates both structural and functional information to assess the relevance of each neural concept. The intuition is that the concept relevance should reflect not only how strongly it is connected to others (structural role), but also how active it is across the time patches (functional role). The hybrid weight-activation importance (HL) can be formulated as follows:

$$\text{HL}(C_i) = \alpha \cdot \text{DC}(C_i) + (1 - \alpha) \cdot \text{MA}(C_i), \quad (8)$$

where $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ is a user parameter that controls the trade-off between structural and functional components. To ensure a fair and balanced integration of these two components, the degree centrality (DC) and mean activation (MA) must be normalized to a common scale before combination. Normalization prevents one component from dominating the hybrid score because of differences in their original scales, and it allows α to adjust their contributions. This step is particularly important since structural and functional measures have different ranges or units, so the HL score accurately balances a concept's connectivity and activity.

5 Empirical studies

In this section, we will assess both the performance and interpretability of LSTCNs through four empirical studies. The first experiment consists of a sensitivity analysis of the LSTCN model to its hyperparameters. The second one compares the forecasting accuracy and training time of the LSTCNs against state-of-the-art recurrent neural networks on real-world data. The third one contrasts the LSTCN model against transformer-based, tree ensemble and hierarchical interpolation forecasters using the M5 competition dataset. In the last experiment, we evaluate the quality of the explanations produced by the proposed SOFI-TSF explainer under different initialization strategies. We compare their quality against a random baseline and a state-of-the-art feature importance method in terms of degradation score Šimić et al. (2022), as a proxy for measuring the faithfulness and sparseness of the feature relevance explanations Nauta et al. (2023).

For all experiments except the third one, we resorted to 25 real-world time series datasets¹ used in Vanhoenshoven et al. (2020), which exhibit different statistical properties. Table 1 portrays an overview of these series datasets, each identified by a unique ID, along with statistical features such as the number of features, length of the time series, mean standard deviation (Std Dev), mean skewness (Skew), mean kurtosis (Kurt), mean absolute correlation (Corr), and mean autocorrelation (Auto) for a maximum time lag of 10. It is worth mentioning that we have normalized the features before computing these statistics to facilitate the analysis across datasets. However, this normalization is not retained when building the forecasting models to avoid information leakage. Concerning the metrics, standard deviation indicates the amount of variation or dispersion in the dataset, as happens with dataset D19, for example. Skewness measures the asymmetry of the distribution, where a positive skew (like 7.87 in D1) indicates a longer tail on the right, while a negative skew (like -0.83 in D25) suggests a longer left tail. Kurtosis indicates the *tailedness* of the distribution, where a high kurtosis value (like 109.27 in D1) translates into a distribution with heavy tails, thus suggesting a higher likelihood of extreme values. Absolute correlation values show the strength of linear relationships between features, while autocorrelation measures how well a dataset correlates with a lagged version of itself. Overall, these statistics provide evidence of the diversity of the selected datasets.

Dataset frequency follows a systematic naming convention based on prefixes. "d-" denotes daily frequency data encompassing financial market indicators (d-sp500-0412, d-vix-0412), equity pairs for trading analysis (d-bhvpale-0206), and multi-asset portfolios (d-xomspaapl). "m-" represents the most extensive category with monthly datasets including macroeconomic indicators such as unemployment statistics across multiple states (m-unemp-states, m-unempstatesAdj, m-3state-un), housing market data (m-houst-nsa, m-hsmort312, m-hsoldhst6312), industrial production components (m-ip3comp, m-ip4comp), bond market indices (m-bnd, m-bndpgsp-6211, m-bndpgsptr), equity-bond combinations (m-pgspabr-6211, m-pgspabt), portfolio deciles for size effects (m-dec12678-6111, m-dec15678-6111), classic equity pairs (m-ibmsp-6111, m-ibmspdx-6111), interest rate spreads (m-cptb3m), and comprehensive macroeconomic

¹The datasets can be downloaded from <http://faculty.chicagobooth.edu/ruey.tsay/teaching/mtsbk>

Table 1: Overview of time series datasets.

ID	Dataset	Features	Length	Std Dev	Skew	Kurt	Corr	Auto
D1	aa-3rv	3	340	0.08	7.87	109.27	0.61	0.10
D2	d-bhpvale-0206	2	946	0.27	0.63	-0.77	0.99	0.99
D3	d-sp500-0412	6	2177	0.18	-0.30	0.26	0.78	0.96
D4	d-vix-0412	4	2177	0.15	2.12	5.75	0.99	0.95
D5	d-xomspaapl	3	1280	0.07	0.13	8.80	0.65	-0.02
D6	m-3state-un	3	407	0.22	1.08	0.93	0.95	0.92
D7	m-bnd	2	609	0.22	0.62	0.21	1.00	0.97
D8	m-bndpgsp-6211	3	600	0.09	-0.05	8.13	0.20	-0.00
D9	m-bndpgspabt	6	600	0.10	0.97	7.55	0.35	0.18
D10	m-cpitb3m	2	792	0.25	0.72	0.03	0.08	0.97
D11	m-dec125910-6111	5	609	0.11	-0.21	2.37	0.85	-0.00
D12	m-dec15678-6111	5	612	0.11	-0.33	2.00	0.91	-0.01
D13	m-houst-nsa	4	648	0.20	0.28	-0.36	0.65	0.54
D14	m-hsmort7112	2	492	0.21	0.34	0.35	0.04	0.92
D15	m-hsoldhst6312	2	595	0.19	0.40	0.17	0.68	0.67
D16	m-ibmsp-6111	2	612	0.11	-0.11	1.83	0.60	0.00
D17	m-ibmspko-6111	3	612	0.11	-0.12	1.90	0.47	0.00
D18	m-ip3comp	3	589	0.29	0.18	-1.21	0.96	1.00
D19	m-ip4comp	4	792	0.30	0.34	-1.06	0.96	1.00
D20	m-pgspabt-6211	3	600	0.10	-0.19	2.35	0.48	-0.01
D21	m-pgspabt	3	600	0.10	-0.19	2.35	0.48	-0.01
D22	m-unemp-states	50	429	0.23	0.69	-0.07	0.66	0.92
D23	m-unempstatesAdj	50	416	0.23	0.73	0.13	0.65	0.92
D24	m-unippmitcu-6712	4	552	0.22	-0.06	-0.08	0.28	0.83
D25	w-fx7	7	606	0.27	0.34	-0.83	0.81	0.98

variables (m-unippmitcu-6712). While "w-" identifies weekly data exemplified by foreign exchange rates across seven major currencies (w-fx7). The dataset aa-3rv, containing realized volatility measures for Alcoa stock, constitutes the sole exception, representing daily frequency data despite its nonstandard prefix. This diverse collection of 25 datasets spans multiple temporal granularities and domains, ranging from high-frequency volatility to macroeconomic trends, providing a robust foundation for evaluating methodologies across varying data characteristics, market conditions, and dimensionalities, including univariate to 50-dimensional multivariate series.

As for the data preparation, we used 80% of each time series for training and validation, while the remaining 20% was used for testing the models' generation ability. Whenever needed, missing values are imputed using an interpolation method based on the nearest point. Moreover, we applied the min-max scaler separately to training, validation, and test sets to obtain scaled errors. In addition, we differentiated the time series to prevent producing shifted predictions where the forecasters tend to reproduce the time series by returning the last observation.

5.1 Performance experiments

The first experiment consists of a sensitivity analysis of the LSTCN model to its hyperparameters (i.e., the number of STCN blocks, the aggregation operator, and the regularization penalty). The number of STCN blocks (time patches) is varied from 1 to 5, while the aggregation operators include the unitary linear, the unitary nonlinear,

the binary maximum, and the binary average operators. Note that increasing the number of STCN blocks further would result in smaller time patches, which will lead to overfitting. At the same time, the regularization penalty takes values in the set $\{0, E-4, E-3, E-2, E-1, 0.5, 1\}$. For all configurations, we will vary the forecasting horizon L from 1 to 5, use the sigmoid function as the activation function, and use the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) as the performance metric. For simplicity, we will only visualize the model’s behavior for odd forecasting horizon values.

Fig. 2 shows the performance difference between the worst and best MAE values attained by the LSTCN model across all settings belonging to the same hyperparameter. For example, Fig. 2(a) depicts the MAE difference when using the best and worst configuration for the number of STCN blocks, averaged over all possible penalty values and aggregation operators. In short, a large value for a given dataset means that optimizing the hyperparameter being analyzed is pivotal for accurate forecasting. In contrast, a small value means that we could use a default hyperparameter value without harming the model’s performance significantly. It is worth mentioning that MAE values correspond to the models’ performance on the test set.

The sensitivity analysis results show interesting patterns. Beginning with the number of STCN blocks, we can notice that the forecasting error increases with longer prediction horizons. This trend indicates that insufficiently fine-tuning this hyperparameter can notably degrade the model’s performance over extended horizons. Moving to the aggregation operator, the results reveal a relatively low impact on error across all forecasting horizons. The MAE differences suggest that the choice of aggregation operator is less relevant and that a default setting may provide acceptable forecasting results without the need for extensive tuning. Lastly, the regularization penalty controlling overfitting exhibits a marked increase in the error as the prediction horizon lengthens, even more noticeable than the trend seen with the number of blocks. Hence, fine-tuning both the number of blocks in the ensemble and the regularization penalty is important for accurate long-term forecasting, while the aggregation operator has a comparatively minor effect on the model’s performance.

In the second experiment, we will contrast the LSTCNs’ performance against state-of-the-art recurrent neural networks: a Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) [Kyunghyun et al. \(2014\)](#), a Long Short-term Memory (LSTM) [Hochreiter and Schmidhuber \(1997\)](#) and a vanilla Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) [Hecht-Nielsen \(1989\)](#). In all cases, we performed hyperparameter tuning through grid search and 5-fold cross-validation, such that 80% is used for training and validation and 20% is used for testing the models’ performance on unseen data. In the case of LSTM, GRU, and RNN, the hyperparameters to be optimized include the learning rate (1.0E-3, 1.0E-2, 1.0E-1) and the batch size (8, 16, 32), while the number of epochs was set to 100. In the case of the LSTCN model, we optimized the regularization penalty (1.0E-3, 1.0E-2, 1.0E-1) and the number of STCN blocks (from 1 to 5). Other hyperparameters, such as the activation function (default: sigmoid) or the aggregation operator (default: unary nonlinear), were not fine-tuned to keep the training time low.

Fig. 3 shows the distribution of test MAE values for all pairs of algorithms involving the LSTCN model. Similarly to the previous experiment, we explored different prediction horizons to assess the models’ ability to cope with long-term forecasting.

Fig. 2: Error sensitivity to hyperparameters for each dataset across different prediction horizons. The hyperparameters concern the number of STCN blocks, the aggregation operator, and the regularization penalty.

The reader can notice that the ideal error distribution should be tight and centered at zero, meaning that the algorithm often makes predictions similar to the ground truth. The error distributions reveal that the LSCTN model produces more accurate predictions as L increases since the network becomes more complex in terms of learnable parameters. In contrast, the other recurrent neural systems involve errors more widely distributed, which indicates less accurate forecasting.

Fig. 3: Distribution of test errors across datasets reported by each recurrent neural system compared to LSTCNs for various prediction horizons.

Fig. 4 depicts a more compact algorithmic comparison. It portrays the test errors averaged across all datasets as reported by each forecasting model for different forecasting horizons. In addition, we display the error bar corresponding to the standard deviation. The results confirm that the LSTCN model significantly outperforms the other recurrent neural networks in terms of test errors as the forecasting horizon L is expanded. It is noticeable that the forecasting error remains fairly steady for different forecasting horizons, as opposed to the other recurrent neural networks. Even in the most challenging setting for the LSTCN model ($L = 1$), it is only outperformed by GRU while performing comparably to LSTM and slightly better than the vanilla RNN model. The LSTCN model reports the smallest standard deviation values, which translates into more robust and reliable predictions.

Fig. 4: Average test errors across all datasets reported by each recurrent neural network for different prediction horizons.

To assess whether performance differences are statistically significant, we conduct a three-step pairwise analysis. First, we apply the Wilcoxon signed-rank test to evaluate whether differences in algorithm performance across datasets are significant, with the null hypothesis H_0 assuming no difference [Wilcoxon \(1945\)](#). Then, we apply Holm’s correction to adjust the resulting p -values and control the family-wise error rate. This adjustment reduces the likelihood of making false positive errors across multiple tests [Benavoli et al. \(2016\)](#). Next, we measure the extent to which the observed performance differences are practically meaningful in real-world scenarios. To do that, we will resort to Cohen’s d measure. It quantifies the effect size by comparing the means of two algorithms’ results and normalizing the difference by how much variability exists in the data (pooled standard deviation). A large absolute Cohen’s d value indicates a significant performance difference, whereas a small absolute value indicates less practical differences. Mathematically, Cohen’s d is expressed as follows:

$$d = \frac{\mu_1 - \mu_2}{\sigma_p} \quad (9)$$

where μ_1 and μ_2 are the sample means of two groups, and σ_p is the pooled standard deviation, representing the overall variability within the groups. For any group size, the pooled standard deviation is calculated as:

$$\sigma_p = \sqrt{\frac{(n_1 - 1)\sigma_1^2 + (n_2 - 1)\sigma_2^2}{n_1 + n_2 - 2}} \quad (10)$$

such that n_1 and n_2 denote the sample sizes, and σ_1 and σ_2 are the standard deviations of the two groups being compared. Standardizing the difference provides a value that describes the difference in terms of standard deviations. If we assume that the first method is the control group and that MAE is the performance metric, then a negative Cohen’s d value indicates that the control group has a lower mean than the comparison group, which translates into better performance.

Tables 2–4 present the Cohen’s d effect size statistic, the p -values reported by the Wilcoxon signed-rank test, and the Holm-corrected p -values. We also indicate whether

the null hypothesis is rejected at the 95% confidence level. Such statistical analysis corresponds to pairwise comparisons in which the LSTCN model serves as the control method across different forecasting horizons.

Table 2: Pairwise statistical results of the Wilcoxon signed test with Holm’s correction and the Cohen’s d effect size statistic, using LSTCNs as the control method ($L = 1$).

Algorithm	Cohen’s d	Wilcoxon p -value	Holm p -value	H_0
GRU	0.3943	3.12E-01	6.30E-01	Fail to reject
LSTM	0.0518	4.26E-01	6.30E-01	Fail to reject
RNN	-0.2877	2.10E-01	6.30E-01	Fail to reject

Table 3: Pairwise statistical results of the Wilcoxon signed test with Holm’s correction and the Cohen’s d effect size statistic, using LSTCNs as the control method ($L = 3$).

Algorithm	Cohen’s d	Wilcoxon p -value	Holm p -value	H_0
GRU	-0.5217	1.48E-01	3.60E-01	Fail to reject
LSTM	-0.4155	2.00E-01	3.60E-01	Fail to reject
RNN	-0.5292	1.20E-01	3.60E-01	Fail to reject

Table 4: Pairwise statistical results of the Wilcoxon signed test with Holm’s correction and the Cohen’s d effect size statistic, using LSTCNs as the control method ($L = 5$).

Algorithm	Cohen’s d	Wilcoxon p -value	Holm p -value	H_0
GRU	-0.3612	2.87E-01	5.74E-01	Fail to reject
LSTM	-0.4462	3.25E-01	5.74E-01	Fail to reject
RNN	-0.7276	1.36E-02	4.07E-02	Reject

The results of the Wilcoxon and Holm tests indicate statistically significant differences between LSTCNs and RNN for the longest prediction horizon ($L = 5$), while no significant differences are observed for other model pairs or prediction horizons at the 0.05 significance level. When forecasting one step ahead, the comparison against RNN reports a moderate negative Cohen’s d value that indicates a practically meaningful difference in favor of LSTCNs. In this setting, LSTCNs are outperformed by GRU and LSTM to a lesser extent, as indicated by the moderate positive Cohen’s d values. However, for forecasting horizons $L = 3$ and $L = 5$, the effect size is always negative with varying extents, with the pair RNN-LSTCNs showing statistically significant differences, reaching a Cohen’s d value of -0.7276. These results indicate that LSTCNs achieve competitive forecasting errors compared to quite powerful deep recurrent networks. This outcome is certainly remarkable for a pure FCM-rooted forecasting

model that implements no hybridization with other machine learning techniques while retaining its inherent interpretability.

To summarize the numerical simulations, Fig. 5 depicts the average performance of each model across all forecasting horizons. More explicitly, we report (a) the average MAE value, and (b) the average log-transformed training time for each forecasting model. Concerning the latter, we have log-transformed the training times for the sake of visualization such that $\log\text{-runtime} = \log_{10}(\text{runtime} + 1)$ such that runtime is the time (in seconds) needed to build the forecasting model. Such a transformation was necessary due to the differences in the training times reported by these recurrent neural networks. It is worth mentioning that the experiments were run on a MacBook Pro with a 1.4 GHz Quad-Core Intel Core i5 processor.

Fig. 5: Average MAE and log-transformed runtime values reported by each forecaster across all time series datasets and forecasting horizons.

It can be seen LSTCN model attains the lowest overall error, followed by GRU and LSTM, while the RNN ranks last. This suggests a positive balance in favor of LSTCNs regardless of the length of the forecasting horizon. Nonetheless, it is fair to mention that LSTCNs were not initially conceived to be more accurate than LSTM or GRU but to be more efficient in terms of training time, as evidenced in Fig. 5(b). It should be stressed that the differences between the log-transformed runtimes account for an exponential magnitude. More explicitly, when reversing the log-transformed runtime, we obtain the following average runtimes in seconds: LSTM (55.23), GRU (55.23), RNN (32.88), and LSTCNs (0.513). This means that LSTCNs are roughly 108 times faster than LSTM and GRU and around 64 times faster than RNN, which is also the least accurate forecaster. Therefore, the competitive forecasting errors reported by the LSTCN model, coupled with its remarkably short training time, make this neural system the clear winner in our empirical study.

In the third experiment, we resort to the M5 forecasting competition dataset [Makridakis et al. \(2022\)](#) as a benchmark to evaluate the performance of LSTCNs alongside state-of-the-art forecasters that do not rely on recurrent architectures. This dataset includes sales data from Walmart stores collected from January 2011 to June 2016. The competition entails a 28-day forecast horizon with 1941 historical data points. The data covers 3,049 products across 10 stores, providing a total of 30,490 individual time series. For simplicity, a subset of data from one store (TX 1) was chosen, resulting in 3,049 individual time series. Data preprocessing involved consolidating separate files that tracked sales history, weekly sales prices, and other temporal features into a single dataset. The missing values in sales prices were set to zero if the product had not been sold during the corresponding period.

The other forecasters are the Temporal Fusion Transformer (TFT) [Lim et al. \(2021\)](#) and the Neural Hierarchical Interpolation for Time Series Forecasting (NHITS) [Challu et al. \(2023\)](#). The TFT model leverages attention mechanisms to capture temporal dependencies in time series data, dynamically selecting relevant time steps to enhance forecast accuracy. The NHITS model decomposes time series data into multiple resolutions to capture seasonal and trend patterns through hierarchical interpolation and frequency-based techniques. In addition, we incorporate the reported results reported by the Light Gradient-Boosting Machine (LightGBM) [Ke et al. \(2017\)](#) on the M5 competition as a baseline comparison for this dataset. Similarly to the previous experiment, we performed hyperparameter tuning for all models. The fine-tuned TFT model uses a hidden state size of 84, a hidden continuous size of 28, a single attention head, and a dropout rate of 0.13, with a learning rate of 0.03. The fine-tuned NHITS model employs an input size of 133, a learning rate of 0.001, a pooling kernel size sequence of [4, 2, 1], and a down-sampling frequency list of [1, 1, 1]. Meanwhile, the best LSTCN model for this dataset uses five STCN blocks, the sigmoid activation function, and a regularization penalty value of 0.25. Figure 6 shows the forecasting errors (measured in terms of MAE) reported by these models.

Fig. 6: MAE comparison for LSTCNs, TFT, NHITS, and LightGBM on the M5 dataset. The LightGBM results represent the competition submission, trained on the full dataset, and are included solely as a baseline reference.

The results show that LSTCNs outperform the other deep learning models on the M5 dataset, achieving a significantly lower MAE than TFT and NHITS. With an error of 1.23, LSTCNs closely approach the accuracy of the baseline, which recorded an error of 0.80. In contrast, the TFT and NHITS models were markedly less precise, with errors of 2.68 and 3.55, respectively. It is important to mention that the results reported for LightGBM correspond to the official competition submission, which includes feature generation steps and training on the full dataset. However, the other models were trained on only 10% of the raw data. For this experiment, training times are not directly comparable, as both TFT and NHITS were run on an Azure Kubernetes Service architecture with GPU support, while the LSTCNs were trained locally. In that regard, LSTCNs’ ability to train on a local setup highlights their computational efficiency and suitability for environments with moderate resources. Therefore, this experiment underscores LSTCNs’ competitiveness with the latest state-of-the-art forecasting models that do not rely on recurrent neural network architectures and their ability to handle long and complex time series.

5.2 Interpretability experiments

Next, we will study the quality of the explanations produced by SOFI-TSF with and without using scoring methods for initializing the seed permutation to be refined. As a reminder, these scoring methods are Degree Centrality (DC), Eigenvector Centrality (EC), Mean Activation (MA), and Hybrid Weight-Activation (HL). In the subsequent experiments, we rely on the best-performing models obtained for the benchmark of 25 time series datasets in the second experiment.

As explained in Sec. 4, the concept importance methods allow aggregating the feature relevance at the level of time patches for visualizing their role in the forecasting. Fig. 7 illustrates the resulting feature relevance scores computed using the DC method on the *m-bndpgspabt* dataset, as an example. The figure displays the six time series variables as parallel plots, each segmented into the optimal number of time patches determined during hyperparameter tuning, two in this case. The prediction of the model is also shown over the test data. The figure highlights the first time patches of the variables *sp* and *abt* as the most important, while the second patches of the first three variables are identified as the least relevant. It should be stressed that the explanations computed in this paper are at a time series feature level, so these colored segments are shown for illustration purposes only.

To evaluate the quality of the explanations produced by our methods, we resort to the perturbation analysis, which is the *de facto* evaluation method for feature importance when ground truth is not available. It quantifies the impact on the model output after perturbing its inputs without undergoing any further retraining. The assumption is that perturbing important features should affect the model’s performance, while perturbing unimportant ones should result in little to no performance degradation. Various perturbation strategies have been proposed Šimić et al. (2022), with their applicability depending on the modality and structure of the data. This consideration is of paramount importance for the analysis, as an inappropriate perturbation strategy may introduce artifacts that inadvertently improve model performance for

Fig. 7: Time patches relevance resulting from aggregating the DC scores for all neural concepts in each time patch for the *m-bndpgspabt* dataset.

Fig. 8: MoRF and LeRF error curves for the *m-bndpgspabt* dataset using (a) the DC method without any optimization and (b) the proposed SOFI-TSF explainer using DC as prior. A rise in error under MoRF and a delayed effect under LeRF indicate accurate attribution, while the grey area between the two curves denotes the degradation score (the larger the area, the sparser the explanation).

some samples Baer et al. (2025). In our experiments, we apply a constant perturbation value that is learned as part of the SOFI-TSF optimization for each dataset and used consistently across all methods to ensure a fair comparison.

Based on the perturbation, we compute the Most Relevant Features First (MoRF) and Least Relevant Features First (LeRF) curves. Recall that in MoRF, the time patches are perturbed in descending order of their assigned importance, whereas in LeRF, the order is ascending. A good attribution method should lead to a substantial performance degradation under the MoRF order, but a delayed effect under the LeRF order. This reflects the expectation that altering truly important features should significantly increase the forecasting error, while changes to irrelevant ones should preserve the core predictive signal until almost all features are perturbed. The steeply increasing MoRF curve (in the case of error as a performance measure) constitutes a proxy for two desired properties of good quality explanations. The first property is faithfulness, which indicates that the feature importance explanation corresponds to the behavior of the model. This means that the features that are signaled as relevant are truly important for the model in order to predict correctly. A steep increase in error and then a plateau also indicates that only a few features are truly significant for the prediction, which translates to the second desired property of sparseness. A shorter set of relevant features should be preferred over a longer one.

Fig. 8 shows the MoRF and LeRF curves for the *m-bndpgspabt* dataset. The first plot presents the results using feature relevance computed with the DC method as the prior, while the second plot displays the relevance scores obtained by SOFI-TSF for the same dataset. The curves in the second plot indicate that SOFI-TSF provides a more faithful and sparser explanation of feature relevance.

Using the area under both curves, we compute the degradation score (DS) metric as the difference between these two areas. Positive values indicate that the attribution

Fig. 9: Degradation score for the proposed SOFI-TSF explainer using different initialization strategies (blue), against a random feature relevance as baseline (grey), and the feature importance rankings obtained by SHAP (brown).

is correct, as MoRF perturbations increase the forecasting error more than LeRF. Negative values point to poor quality attributions due to LeRF perturbations disrupting the predictions more than MoRF, which goes against intuition.

Fig. 9 shows the degradation scores for SOFI-TSF variants (in blue), contrasted with a random baseline (in grey) and SHAP feature importance [Lundberg and Lee \(2017\)](#) (in brown), aggregated across all datasets in the study. The random baseline obtains score values ranging from negative to positive small values, indicating that random attributions are of poor quality and that not all concepts contribute equally to forecasting. Regarding our methods, all SOFI-TSF variants outperform the SHAP baseline by a significant margin. Furthermore, incorporating priors from intrinsic concept importance methods improves upon the scores obtained by SOFI-TSF alone, with varying extents. This means that although SOFI-TSF is capable of finding good-quality explanations, there is value in providing prior information on feature relevance as well. In particular, the method EC obtains the best degradation scores among all variants. While DC captures how connected a concept is in the network, EC rewards concepts that are connected to other important concepts, which encodes recursive or systemic influence. This broader structural perspective might explain its superior performance.

To determine whether the differences in the degradation scores are statistically significant, we use the pairwise Wilcoxon test with Holm’s correction. We also compute Cohen’s d statistic to quantify the effect size of the differences, which quantifies the practical significance of these differences. Table 5 shows the results of the statistical analysis for all the pairs with SOFI-TSF as a control method. Based on these results, all pairwise comparisons between SOFI-TSF and the other attribution methods produce statistically significant differences, as indicated by the Wilcoxon p -values and Holm-corrected p -values being below the 0.05 threshold. This suggests that SOFI-TSF consistently differs meaningfully from the compared methods in terms of degradation score performance. The effect sizes, measured using Cohen’s d , provide further insight

Table 5: Pairwise statistical results of the Wilcoxon signed test with Holm’s correction and the Cohen’s d effect size statistic, using SOFI-TSF as the control method.

Method	Cohen’s d	Wilcoxon p -value	Holm p -value	H_0
RAND	1.30E+00	3.28E-06	1.64E-05	Reject
DC	-3.15E-01	1.01E-05	4.03E-05	Reject
EC	-3.11E-01	2.66E-05	7.99E-05	Reject
MA	-2.98E-01	1.36E-02	1.47E-02	Reject
HL	-2.88E-01	7.37E-03	1.47E-02	Reject
SHAP	1.40E+00	5.96E-08	3.58E-07	Reject

into the magnitude of these differences. Since higher degradation scores indicate better performance, higher values of d are desirable for the control method. The comparisons between SOFI-TSF and the random and SHAP baselines show very large effect sizes ($d > 1.30$), suggesting a substantial performance gap in favor of SOFI. Furthermore, the comparisons between SOFI-TSF and all concept importance methods used as priors (DC, EC, MA, HL) show a moderate effect size ($-0.31 < d < -0.28$) in favor of the latter, suggesting that these methods achieve somewhat similar results among them, and they all outperform the use of SOFI-TSF without priors.

All SOFI-based methods outperform a random assignment of relevance scores, which confirms that not all LSTCN concepts contribute equally to prediction and that meaningful attribution is achievable. While the proposed SOFI-TSF explainer for forecasting performs successfully as a model-agnostic post-hoc method applied to a trained LSTCN, the intrinsic concept importance methods offer complementary insights by analyzing the network structure. These methods serve as valuable knowledge priors for SOFI, which allow for enhancing its explanatory power.

6 Concluding remarks

In this paper, we have investigated the effectiveness, efficacy, and interpretability of LSTCN forecasting models using real-world time series data. This brand-new model uses the principles of fuzzy cognitive mapping, where all neural concepts and weights carry a well-defined meaning for the problem domain. The absence of hidden neurons is the cornerstone of the interpretability features of this deep learning model, even when the raw explanations derived directly from the weight set are often subpar in terms of faithfulness and sparsity. Concerning our contributions, we proposed the SOFI-TSF explainer for generating a ranking of temporal features that maximizes sparsity. This explainer can be applied to any forecaster, yet it supports prior knowledge approximating the solution, if available. In addition, we performed a hyperparameter sensitivity analysis and conducted a large experimental analysis contrasting LSTCNs’ performance against recurrent neural networks, a transformer model, a gradient boosting machine, and a hierarchical interpolation model.

The sensitivity analysis indicated that the number of STCN blocks in the ensemble and the regularization penalty controlling overfitting are important hyperparameters that need to be carefully tuned. In contrast, the aggregation operator responsible for producing the knowledge to be passed to the following STCN block was found to be

less relevant. As for the comparison with other forecasters, the numerical simulations indicated that LSTCNs produce comparable or smaller forecasting errors than the recurrent neural network forecasters used in our study, while being around 100 times faster to train on average. In addition, LSTCNs outperformed other powerful methods (such as TFT and NHITS) on a 10% sample of the M5 forecasting dataset, which is regarded as a complex forecasting problem. It was observed that LSTCNs' performance on the sampled dataset is reasonably closer to the LightGBM baseline trained on the whole dataset. Concerning the interpretability assessment, the proposed SOFI-TSF explainer easily outperformed the baselines for all initialization variants, yet eigenvalue centrality emerged as the best initialization strategy.

Future research steps will be devoted to improving the LSTCN model by addressing its symmetric reasoning to break the trade-off between the benefits of using longer sequences from the past and the error degradation of longer prediction horizons. More explicitly, we believe that the symmetric architecture limits the model's predictive power since the forecasting horizon defines the number of steps in the past used to make predictions. Addressing that issue would also allow the model to incorporate static features that do not change over time while keeping the knowledge transfer mechanism intact. Another interesting aspect to be studied concerns the model's effectiveness when varying the amount of training data. For example, the LSTCNs' remarkable performance when trained on only 10% of the M5 dataset relative to the LightGBM baseline trained on the whole dataset invites optimism.

Availability of data and material

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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